

Factors Influencing the Performance of Factory Employees in Indonesian Automotive Manufacturing Company

(Case Study at PT. DI)

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Abstract:- There is a phenomenon at PT. DI is one of the automotive manufacturing companies in Indonesia, namely the non-achievement of productivity ratios, high customer claims, and reject product ratios in the last 3 years. Based on the results of pre-research found that there are 2 variables that most affect performance at PT. DI so the purpose of this study is to see the effect of job satisfaction on the performance of factory employees with work discipline as an intervening variable at PT. DI. This study uses a quantitative approach using primary data through questionnaires with a purposive sampling method to 127 respondents who are leaders, foreman, and supervisors who work in the factory. The data analysis technique uses Partial Least Square (PLS) using SmartPLS 3.2.9. The results show that job satisfaction positively and significantly affect employee performance, work discipline positively and significantly affect employee performance, job satisfaction has a positive significant effect on work discipline. Job satisfaction has a positive significant effect on performance through work discipline.

Keywords:- Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline, Manufacture, Automotive.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, the manufacturing industry in Indonesia has an important role in economic growth where in the second quarter of 2021 it contributed 6.91% of the total growth of 7.07%. One of the manufacturing subsectors that has an important role in the automotive industry. This is evidenced by the total export of four or more wheeled vehicles and their components in January-April 2021 amounting to IDR 29.88 trillion. As a manufacturing company engaged in the production of automotive components, PT DI needs to continue to improve its performance in maintaining the company's competitive level. Therefore, the company needs to maintain and improve its factory operations to achieve productivity, quality, and customer satisfaction. To achieve what is targeted, employees become one of the most important aspects since Indonesian automotive manufacturing companies are labor-intensive

companies that are highly dependent on the performance of their employees.

According to data obtained from the Quality Assurance (QA) Division in 2019 - 2021, customer claims are quite high and tend to increase yearly, as shown in Fig. 1 and some cases occur due to human factors.

Fig 1 PT DI Customer Claim Data for 2019 - 2021

In addition to the condition of customer claims that have increased in the last 3 years, another condition that is also of concern is the productivity ratio of PT DI in producing its products. Taken from the Production division data, the factory productivity ratio is still quite low, which is below 90% in the last 3 years, namely 2019 - 2021 as described in Fig. 2.

Fig 2 PT. DI Productivity Ratio Data for 2019-2021

Another condition that is quite a concern in seeing the company's performance is the ability of the process not to produce Not Good (NG) or defective products. From the data obtained from the Production division, the number of NG products produced in the factory tends to increase every year as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 PT. DI Total not Good Product for 2019-2021

Kasmir (2016) states that 13 factors affect performance in both results and work behavior: Ability / Skills, Knowledge, Work Design, Personality, Work motivation, Leadership, Leadership Style, Organizational culture, Job satisfaction, Work environment, Loyalty, Commitment, and Work discipline. Therefore, a pre-survey was made to 21 leaders, 5 foreman, and 14 supervisors to see the factors that most affect the performance of PT DI factory employees. The results of the pre-survey are shown in Table 1, namely the 3 most dominant factors with values above not above 50% are job satisfaction (55%), work environment (55%), and work discipline (75%).

Table 1 PT. DI Pre-Survey Result

No	Factor affect to Performance	Result
1	Ability/Skills	33%
2	Knowledge	23%
3	Work Design	20%
4	Personality	38%
5	Motivation	10%
6	Leadership	25%
7	Leadership Style	3%
8	Organizational Culture	23%
9	Job Satisfaction	55%
10	Work Environment	45%
11	Loyalty	45%
12	Commitment	8%
13	Work Discipline	70%

Based on the phenomena that occur at PT DI and the results of the pre-survey above, the purpose of this study is to analyze and investigate the effect of job satisfaction and work discipline on employee performance at PT DI.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ Human Resource Management

According to Hasibuan (2019), human resource management is the science and art of managing the relationship and role of the workforce so that it effectively and efficiently helps realize the goals of the company, employees, and society.

According to Hasibuan (2019), human resource functions include planning, organizing, directing, controlling, procuring, developing, compensating, integrating, maintaining, disciplining, and dismissing.

Human resource strategy emphasizes the need for human resource planning and the implementation of strategies to be formulated in the context of organizational strategy. The strategy as a whole is responsive to changes in the organization's external environment and thus requires interpretation and adaptation by practitioners to ensure compatibility between the human resource strategy and the organization's business plan. With the important role of human resources in an organization in achieving goals, one of the important things is how to manage and evaluate the performance of each element of human resources to have a positive impact on the organization or often referred to as performance management.

➤ Employee Performance

According to Afandi (2018), performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company following their respective authorities and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals legally, not against the law, and not against morals and ethics. According to Mangkunegara (2017), there are 4 dimensions of employee performance, they are quality of work, quantity of work, execution of task, and work responsibility.

➤ Work Discipline

According to Rivai (2017), work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change a behavior and as an effort to increase the awareness and willingness of a person to comply with all company regulations. According to Robbin & Judge (2015), job satisfaction will affect employee discipline, such as absence rates. Dissatisfied employees are more likely to leave their jobs. When a number of jobs are available, dissatisfied workers have a high absence rate. And according to Davis and Newstrom quoted by Sinambela (2012), dissatisfied employees tend to be absent more often. According to Siswanto (2013), there are several dimensions of work discipline as follows: frequency of attendance, employee alertness, adherence to work standards, adherence to work rules, and work ethics.

➤ Job Satisfaction

According to Robbins & Judge (2017), job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude toward his job. Work requires interaction with colleagues of all human elements in the organization and obligations in following organizational rules and policies. According to Afandi (2018), the

dimensions of job satisfaction include work, wages, promotions, supervisors, and coworkers.

➤ *Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis*

Based on several theories and previous research, the conceptual framework in this study can be seen in Fig. 4, and based on this framework, there are 4 hypotheses proposed.

Every employee certainly wants to get job satisfaction in his job. This job satisfaction can be fulfilled from various aspects such as appropriate work and is also influenced by the employees themselves (Mangkunegara, 2017). Some previous studies also state that job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on performance such as research conducted by Miah (2018), Herianto & Widigdo (2022), Rejeki, R.T., Widigdo, (2021), Rinaldi and Riyanto (2021). Based on the theory and previous research, a hypothesis was made as below :

- *H1: Job Satisfaction has a Positive and Significant effect on the Performance of Factory Employees*

Work discipline concerns the awareness and willingness of a person to fulfill all company regulations (Rivai, 2017), which of course can affect the achievement of an employee's performance because a company goal cannot be achieved without being based on compliance with applicable regulations in the company. This is supported by the results of previous studies which say that work discipline affects performance positively and significantly as a result of research conducted by Wardani & Riyanto (2019), Hamid & Riyanto (2020). Based on the theory and previous research, a hypothesis was made as below :

- *H2: Work Discipline has a Positive and Significant Effect on the Performance of Factory Employees*

Job satisfaction describes a person's level of excitement about the work he does based on the degree of conformity between the individual and the organization so that if job satisfaction can be increased, it will have an impact on his desire to comply with applicable regulations within the company. Based on previous research conducted by Winarsih & Fariz (2021) stated that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. Based on the theory and previous research, a hypothesis was made as below :

- *H3: Job Satisfaction has a Positive and Significant Effect on the Work Discipline of Factory Employees*

Good work discipline can be a good medium for every employee in achieving good performance. In this case, either job satisfaction or work environment if through good work discipline it should further improve the performance of an employee. Based on previous research conducted by Jufrizen & Sitorus (2021), work discipline can mediate job satisfaction on performance. Based on the theory and previous research, a hypothesis was made as below :

- *H4: Job Satisfaction has a Positive and Significant Effect on the Performance of Factory Employees with the Mediation of Work Discipline.*

Fig 4 Research Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The research design used is quantitative research in the form of associative research using primary data. The population in this study were leaders, foreman, and supervisors at the PT DI factory with a total of 185 people then using the Slovin formula with an accuracy rate of 95%, the sample taken was 127 respondents. Primary data was taken using a questionnaire with a Likert scale between 1-5 on 4 research variables. The independent variables in this study are job satisfaction (X) while the dependent variable is employee performance (Y) and work discipline (Z) as mediating variable. Dimensions and indicators of each variables are described on Table 2 below.

Table 2 Operational Variables

Variable	Dimension	Indicator
Job Satisfaction (X) Afandi (2018)	Jobs	Level of job difficulty
		Suitability with education
	Wages	Decent work wage
		Salary increase
	Promotion	Functional position opportunities Grade advancement opportunities
	Supervisor	Supportive supervisor
		Competent Supervisor
Coworkers	Supportive coworkers	
Work Discipline (Z) Siswanto (2013)	Frequency of Attendance	Timely attendance of employees at work
		On-time attendance at work
	Vigilance Level	Thoroughness in work
		Calculations in decisions
	Adherence to Work Standards	Adhere to work guidelines
		Responsibility at work
Adherence to Work Rules	Compliance with regulations	
	Ease of work	
Work Ethics	Harmonious work atmosphere	
	Mutual respect between employees	
Employee Performance (Y) Mangkunegara (2017)	Work Quality	Improved quality / work standards
		Increased work ability
	Work Quantity	Achievement of work quantity
		Achievement of work productivity
	Task Implementation	Work as directed by superiors
		Work with focus and accuracy
	Responsibility	Carry out work with full awareness
		Responsible for work results

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Respondents Characteristic*

Based on Table 3 below, characteristics of respondents in this study in terms of positions consisted of 67% leaders, 18% foreman, and 16% supervisors. Meanwhile, in terms of work location, 65% work in the second plant and 35% work in the third plant. While in terms of age, 27% are 18-30 years old, 18% are 31-40 years old, 50% are 41-50 years old and only 5% are over 50 years old. From the characteristics of the respondents above, it can be seen that the respondents are dominated by senior employees who are over 41 years old with the majority being in leader positions because of the 3 positions, the leader position is the position with the largest population.

Table 3. Characteristics of respondents

Information	Frequency (person)	Percentage (%)
Title		
Leader	85	67%
Foreman	23	18%
Supervisor	19	15%
Plant		
Bekasi	83	65%
Fajar	44	35%
Sex		
Male	125	98%
Female	2	2%
Age (years)		
18-30	34	27%
31-40	23	18%
41-50	64	50%
>50	6	5%
Service Term (years)		
<5	8	6%
6-10	30	24%
11-15	18	14%
16-20	2	2%
21-25	41	32%
26-30	24	19%
>30	4	3%

Table 4 Cross Loading Value

	JOB SATISFACTION (X)	WORK DISCIPLINE (Z)	EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE (Y)	REMARKS
KK1.1	0.687	0.520	0.514	VALID
KK1.2	0.741	0.338	0.431	VALID
KK2.1	0.533	0.224	0.087	VALID
KK2.2	0.599	0.238	0.120	VALID
KK3.1	0.647	0.328	0.271	VALID
KK3.2	0.736	0.369	0.371	VALID
KK4.1	0.660	0.399	0.355	VALID
KK4.2	0.676	0.391	0.340	VALID
KK5.1	0.619	0.256	0.266	VALID
KK5.2	0.552	0.401	0.453	VALID
DK1.1	0.359	0.655	0.456	VALID
DK1.2	0.383	0.728	0.463	VALID
DK2.1	0.445	0.763	0.603	VALID
DK2.3	0.191	0.588	0.447	VALID
DK3.1	0.396	0.641	0.407	VALID
DK3.2	0.386	0.697	0.450	VALID
DK4.1	0.431	0.684	0.611	VALID
DK4.2	0.495	0.664	0.582	VALID
DK5.1	0.318	0.761	0.544	VALID
DK5.2	0.320	0.712	0.600	VALID
K1.1	0.357	0.441	0.713	VALID
K1.2	0.393	0.403	0.546	VALID
K2.1	0.405	0.576	0.760	VALID
K2.2	0.444	0.574	0.718	VALID
K3.1	0.444	0.608	0.786	VALID
K3.2	0.389	0.643	0.816	VALID
K4.1	0.273	0.567	0.778	VALID
K4.2	0.292	0.568	0.706	VALID

➤ *Outer Model Measurement Convergent Validity*

In testing the convergent validity of data from the sample results on 127 respondents, testing was carried out 2 times until all indicators were valid and it was found that there were 28 valid indicators while 4 indicators were invalid so they were removed from the research model so that the research model after removing 4 indicators can be seen in Fig. 5.

➤ *Outer Model Measurement Discriminant Validity*

Based on Table 4 below, the discriminant validity test is carried out by looking at the cross-loading value, and total indicators used in this study are valid evidenced by the cross loading value of each variable which is higher than the other construct variables.

➤ *Outer Model Measurement Composite Reliability*

Then to see the reliability value of the research construct based on the composite reliability value and Cronbach's alpha, the reliable value is obtained above 0.7 as illustrated in Table 5 (Hair et al., 2018)

Table 5 Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha Score

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability
Employee Performance (Y)	0.874	0.881	0.901
Work Discipline (Z)	0.852	0.887	0.878
Job Satisfaction (X)	0.845	0.852	0.878

➤ *Inner Model Measurement Determinant Coefficient (R²)*

Then the R² value is tested to show how much influence the exogenous variables have on the endogenous variables In this case, the endogenous variable, namely performance (Y) and the intervening variable (Z), is influenced by the endogenous variables, namely job satisfaction (X). The R² value can be seen in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Result of R² score

Variables	R ²	R ² Adjusted
Employee Performance (Y)	0.582	0.575
Work Discipline (Z)	0.294	0.288

Based on Table 4 above, it can be seen that the value of the coefficient of determination (R²) of the Work Discipline variable (Z) is 0.294. These results explain that the exogenous variables, namely job satisfaction (X) have an influence of 29.4% on the work discipline variable (Z) while the remaining 71.6% is influenced by other variables. According to Ghozali (2014) that the results of the coefficient of determination (R²) values of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 indicate that the model is good,

moderate, and weak. So it can be concluded that the variable effect of job satisfaction (X) on work discipline (Z) has a weak coefficient of determination. Then for the R² value on the performance variable (Y), namely 0.582, it means that the variable is influenced by the variables of job satisfaction (X), and work discipline (Z), which is 58.2% while the rest is influenced by other variables. This shows that the coefficient of determination is moderate.

Fig 5 Outer Model Measurement (Loading Factor)

➤ Inner Model Measurement Bootstrapping Direct Effect

The next test is hypothesis testing (T-test) by looking at the coefficient path and looking at the T statistic value compared to the t table and P-Value. This study using the standard t-table value using the following formula:

$$df = n - k = 127 - 4 = 123$$

• Description:

- ✓ n = number of samples
- ✓ k = number of variables

Based on the above formula with a significant level (α) of 0.05, the t-table value is 1.979 so the variable is declared to have good significance if the t-statistic > 1.979 while the P-Value is considered significant if the value is < 0.05.

Table 7 Bootstrapping Test Direct Effect Result

Variables	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Remarks
Job Satisfaction (X) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.144	2.064	0.041	Positive, Significant
Work Discipline (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.542	9.092	0.000	Positive, Significant
Job Satisfaction (X) -> Work Discipline (Z)	0.675	12.750	0.000	Positive, Significant

➤ The Results of Hypothesis Testing using Bootstrapping can be Seen in Table 7 that:

- The job satisfaction variable (X) on the performance variable (Y) has a positive original sample value of 0.144 with a T statistic value of 2.064 which is higher than the T table which is 1.979 and has a P-Value of 0.041 which is lower than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the job satisfaction variable (X) has a positive significant influence on the performance variable (Y).
- The work discipline variable (Z) on the performance variable (Y) has a positive original sample value of 0.675 and has a T statistic value of 9.092 > t table namely 1.979 and a P value of 0 which is lower than 0.05. It can be concluded that the work discipline variable (Z) has a positive and significant effect on the performance variable (Y).

- The variable job satisfaction (X) on work discipline (Z) has a positive original sample value of 0.542 and a statistical T value is 12.750 which is higher than 1.979 and a P value of 0 that lower than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the job satisfaction variable (X) has a positive significant effect on the work discipline variable (Z).

➤ Inner Model Measurement Bootstrapping Indirect Effect

After the direct effect coefficient path analysis is carried out, the coefficient path analysis is also carried out for the indirect effect in this research model with the same standards as the coefficient path analysis, namely the comparison of the T statistic value > 1.979 and P Value > 0.05 and the results can be seen in table 8 which shows that:

Fig 6 The Result of T Statistic from Bootstrapping

The job satisfaction variable (X) on the performance variable (Y) indirectly through the work discipline variable (Z) has a positive original sample value of 0.366 and the T statistic value is 6.704 which is higher than the t table of 1.979

and the P-Value is 0 which lower than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the job satisfaction variable (X) has a positive significant effect on the performance variable (Y) indirectly through the work discipline variable (Z).

Table 8 Bootstrapping Test Indirect Effect Result

Variables	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Remarks
Job Satisfaction (X) -> Work Discipline (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.366	6.704	0.000	Positive, Significant

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the previous bootstrapping calculations which can be seen in Fig. 6. The results showed that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of factory employees so hypothesis 1 is accepted. This means that the better the job satisfaction of employees at PT DI, it will affect the better performance of PT DI factory employees. This is in accordance with research conducted by Miah (2018), Herianto & Widigdo (2022), Rejeki, R.T., Widigdo, (2021), Rinaldi and Riyanto (2021). Also based on Fig. 6 that the most influential indicator is job where the workload is in accordance with the position and satisfaction with the completion of tasks is something that needs to be considered by PT. DI.

Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance so hypothesis 2 is accepted. Even from the results of bootstrapping analysis, work discipline has the greatest influence on performance compared to job satisfaction. This means that the better a person's work discipline, the better his performance at PT DI. This is in accordance with research conducted by Wardani & Riyanto (2019), Hamid & Riyanto (2020). Based on Fig. 6, the highest outer model score is vigilance level which means every employee needs to emphasize discipline in work vigilance such as thoroughness in making quality products and always reporting to superiors if there are problems that could threaten product quality.

Job satisfaction has a positive significant effect on work discipline so hypothesis 3 is accepted. This means that the better a person's job satisfaction, the better his performance will be in accordance with previous research conducted by Winarsih & Fariz (2021). It can be concluded that if job satisfaction, especially on the most influencing factor, namely satisfaction with the work carried out, can be fulfilled, it will support the creation of good work discipline.

Job satisfaction has a positive significant effect on the performance of factory employees with the mediation of work discipline so hypothesis 4 is accepted. From the previous results that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of factory employees directly (direct effect) so it can be concluded that work discipline has mediating role for the job satisfaction variable on performance. This is in accordance with research conducted by Jufrizen & Sitorus (2021).

In addition, we see in Fig. 6 that of the 2 exogenous variables, work discipline has a greater influence on employee performance compared to job satisfaction variables. This is in line with the actual conditions that occurred at PT. In manufacturing companies, especially in the factory operations section, discipline is the most important factor in achieving performance. Starting from discipline towards work regulations such as timely attendance to compliance with work standards such as SOP, this will greatly affect product quality and work productivity at the factory.

VI. CONCLUSION

➤ *Based on the results of data analysis and proof of hypotheses on phenomena that occur at PT DI, the following conclusions can be drawn:*

- Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of factory employees at PT. DI.
- Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on the performance of factory employees at PT. DI.
- Job satisfaction has a positive but insignificant effect on the performance of PT. DI factory employees.
- Job satisfaction has a positive but insignificant effect on the performance of factory employees with the mediation of work discipline at PT. DI.

SUGGESTION

➤ *Based on the results of the analysis and conclusions generated in this study, some suggestions that can be given are as follows:*

- To be able to improve the performance of factory employees at PT DI, the company should focus on increasing job satisfaction and work discipline. Work discipline has a more significant effect than job satisfaction so company policies can be focused on supporting the creation of good work discipline such as rewards and punishments for each employee who is the most disciplined and for those who are not disciplined.
- To increase job satisfaction, the company needs to pay attention to the satisfaction of factory employees achieved by the implementation of good work by each factory employee and provide work according to their position. This can be done by carrying out procedures for leaders to be able to see their work regularly to ensure that employees are satisfied enough with the support to achieve their work targets.

- To improve work discipline, the company needs to create a harmonious atmosphere in the workplace between factory employees and maintain mutual ethics between factory employees. The company needs to focus on creating harmonious relationships between employees with several activities such as gathering for building open communication between employees.
- To be able to improve work discipline, the company needs to pay attention to vigilance level. Several strategies can be carried out through increasing supervision and vigilance of the work discipline of employees both in compliance with regulations such as periodic checking of employee absences every day and compliance with work standards by periodically checking employee compliance with SOPs.

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